

Heterocyclic Compounds from β -Diketones. Part II. Sulphanilamidoazoacetoacetates and their Cyclisation

Anil Prakash and I. R. Gambhir

Sulphanilamidoazoacetoacetates have been obtained by coupling the diazotised solutions of sulphanilamide, sulphacetamide, and sulphanilic acid with ethyl acetoacetate. These have been interconverted and cyclised into pyrazolones, pyrazolone amides, and isoxazolone derivatives. With hydrochloric acid these form sulphanilidophenylhydrazones of α -keto-propaldehyde.

The diazotised solutions of sulphanilamide, sulphacetamide, and sulphanilic acid have been found to react with ethanolic solution of ethyl acetoacetate in presence of sodium acetate to yield sulphanilamido-(I), sulphanilacetamido-(II), and sulphonophenyl-azoacetoacetate (III).

- (I): R = $-\text{NH}_2$; R' = $-\text{COOEt}$.
(II): R = $-\text{NHCOMe}$; R' = $-\text{COOEt}$.
(III): R = $-\text{OH}$; R' = $-\text{COOEt}$
(IV): R = $-\text{NH}_2$; R' = $-\text{H}$.
(V): R = $-\text{NHCOMe}$, R' = $-\text{H}$.
(VI): R = $-\text{OH}$; R' = $-\text{H}$.
(VII): R = $-\text{Cl}$; R' = $-\text{COOEt}$.

The behaviour of compounds (I), (II), and (III) towards hydrazine hydrate, semicarbazide acetate, phenylhydrazine, and hydroxylamine acetate to yield pyrazolones, pyrazolone amides, phenylpyrazolones, and isoxazolone derivatives is identical with those of sulphanilamidobenzeneazoacetoacetate¹. When heated with hydrochloric acid in ethanolic or acetic acid solution, the compounds (I-III) are converted into sulphanilamido-(IV), sulphacetamido-(V), and sulphonophenyl-(VI) phenylhydrazones of α -keto-propaldehyde, respectively, by cleavage of the ethoxycarbonyl group; the intermediate compounds containing carboxylic group (R' = $-\text{COOH}$) could not, however, be isolated. The structure of the compounds (IV-VI) are evident from their IR spectra, which show peaks for a conjugated CO and NH and none for an ester group.

Sulphonophenylazoacetoacetate (III) with thionyl chloride forms phenylchlorosulphonylazoacetoacetate (VII). The latter on treatment with ammonia is converted into sulphanilamidoazoacetoacetate (I), which on subsequent acetylation furnishes sulphanilacetamidoazoacetoacetate (II).

1. Prakash and Gambhir, this *Journal*, 1963, 40, 847.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sulphanilamidoazoacetate (I).—A diazotised solution of sulphanilamide (1.7g.) was mixed with the cooled mixture of sodium acetate (50 g.), ethyl acetoacetate (1.3g.), water (20 ml), and ethanol (20 ml) and the mixture shaken vigorously. A pale yellow precipitate separated, which on recrystallisation from ethanol provided 82% of sulphanilamidoazoacetate in golden yellow needles, m.p. 127°. (Found: S, 10.10. $C_{12}H_{13}O_5N_3S$ requires S, 10.22%).

2,4-DNP of compound (I) was obtained as orange plates from acetic acid, m.p. 203°. (Found: S, 6.32. $C_{18}H_{20}O_8N_7S$ requires S, 6.47%).

3-Methyl-4-sulphanilamidoazo-5-pyrazolone.—A solution of compound (I) (3.1g.), glacial acetic acid (8 ml), and hydrazine hydrate (1.0 g.) were heated for 2 hours. On cooling and adding water, a yellow precipitate separated, which on recrystallisation from ethanol furnished 73% of the pure product as lemon-yellow needles, m.p. 280°. (Found: S, 11.24. $C_{10}H_{11}O_3N_3S$ requires S, 11.38%).

3-Methyl-4-sulphanilamidoazo-5-pyrazolone-1-amide.—A solution of compound (I) (3.1 g.) in ethanol (8 ml), semicarbazide hydrochloride (1.0 g.), and sodium acetate (0.5 g.) were refluxed for 2 hours. On adding water, a precipitate separated, which on recrystallisation from ethanol afforded 70% of the pure product in pale yellow needles, m.p. 235°. (Found: S, 9.79. $C_{11}H_{13}O_4N_6S$ requires S, 9.87%).

3-Methyl-1-phenyl-4-sulphanilamidoazo-5-pyrazolone.—A solution of compound (I) (3.1 g.) in glacial acetic acid (8 ml) and phenylhydrazine (1.0 g.) was heated for 2 hours and cooled. A solid separating was recrystallised from acetic acid in orange needles in 75% yield, m.p. 258°. (Found: S, 8.89. $C_{15}H_{13}O_3N_3S$ requires S, 8.96%).

3-Methyl-1-(p-tolyl)-4-sulphanilamidoazo-5-pyrazolone was prepared from p-tolylhydrazine and compound (I). It was recrystallised from ethanol in 71% yield as reddish plates, m.p. 249°. (Found: S, 8.51. $C_{17}H_{17}O_3N_3S$ requires S, 8.62%).

3-Methyl-1-chlorophenyl-4-sulphanilamidoazo-5-pyrazolone, prepared from p-chlorophenylhydrazine and compound (I), was recrystallised from ethanol in 70% yield as reddish yellow plates, m.p. 237°. (Found: S, 8.08. $C_{15}H_{14}O_3N_3ClS$ requires S, 8.17%).

3-Methyl-4-sulphanilamidoazo-5-isoxazolone.—A solution of compound (I) (3.1g.) in ethanol (8 ml), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1.0 g.), and sodium acetate (0.5 g.) were refluxed for 2 hours. On adding water, a precipitate separated, which was recrystallised from acetic acid in 68% yield as lemon-yellow needles, m.p. 230°. (Found: S, 11.27. $C_{10}H_{10}O_4N_4S$ requires S, 11.34%).

Sulphamidophenylhydrazone of α -Keto-propaldehyde (IV).—A solution of compound (I) (3.1 g.) in ethanol (15 ml) was refluxed with HCl (dil., 30 ml) for 2 hours. On cooling, a golden yellow precipitate separating was recrystallised from glacial acetic acid as golden yellow flakes, m.p. 213°, yield 81%. (Found: S, 13.20. $C_9H_7O_3N_3S$ requires S, 13.27%).

Sulphanilacetamidoazoacetate (II): *Method A*.—The diazotised solution of sulphacetamide (2.4 g.) was mixed with the cooled mixture of ethyl acetoacetate (1.5 g.),

ethanol (15 ml), water (15 ml), and sodium acetate (60 g.); the mixture was shaken vigorously. A yellow product separated, which on recrystallisation from ethanol provided 82% of the product (II) as golden yellow prisms, m.p. 203°. (Found: S, 8.92. $C_{14}H_{17}O_6N_3S$ requires S, 9.01%).

Method B.—A solution of compound (I) in acetyl chloride (12 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 3 hours. On cooling and dilution, a dirty yellow solid separated, which on recrystallisation from ethanol furnished 60% of compound (II). Its mixed m.p. with the one obtained by method A remained undepressed.

2,4-DNP of compound (II) was obtained as orange-red needles from ethanol, m.p. 270°. (Found: S, 5.86. $C_{20}H_{22}O_9N_3S$ requires S, 5.97%).

Sulphacetamidophenylhydrazone of α -keto-propaldehyde (V) was prepared from compound (II) and HCl in the same way as in compound (IV). Recrystallisation from acetic acid afforded 80% of the product (V) in golden yellow flakes, m.p. 318°. (Found: S, 11.26. $C_{11}H_{13}O_4N_3S$ requires S, 11.31%).

Sulphonophenylazoacetoacetate (III).—Sulphanilic acid (1.7 g.), dissolved in water (50 ml) containing NaOH (0.5 g.) and sodium nitrite (0.6 g.), was slowly added to a solution of HCl (conc., 10 ml) in ice-cold water (70 g.). The diazotised solution of sulphanilic acid, so obtained, was then poured with stirring on a solution comprising sodium acetate (50 g.), ethylacetoacetate (1.5 g.), ethanol (15 ml), ice, and water (100 g.). The cold mixture was acidified to Congo-red paper with HCl. The product separating was recrystallised from ethanol in 78% yield as yellow prisms, m.p. 207°. (Found: S, 10.11. $C_{12}H_{14}O_6N_2S$ requires S, 10.19%).

2,4-DNP of compound (III) was obtained as red plates from ethanol, m.p. 275°. (Found: S, 6.36. $C_{18}H_{19}O_9N_6S$ requires S, 6.46%).

Sulphonophenylhydrazone of α -keto-propaldehyde (VI) was obtained from compound (III) and HCl similarly as compound (IV). Recrystallisation from acetic acid furnished 79% of the product (VI) as yellow needles, m.p. 320°. (Found: S, 13.14. $C_9H_{10}O_4N_2S$ requires S, 13.22%).

Phenyl chloro sulphonylazoacetoacetate (VII).—Sulphonophenylazoacetoacetate (III) (3.1 g.) was heated with thionyl chloride (8.0 g.) on a water bath for 3 hours. On cooling, a product separated, which on recrystallisation from ethanol furnished the product (VII) in golden yellow prisms, m.p. 94°. (Found: S, 9.54. $C_{12}H_{13}O_5N_2ClS$ requires S, 9.62%).

On warming with ammonia and cooling, it provided golden yellow needles of sulphanilamidoazoacetoacetate(I), m.p. 127°.

The pyrazolones, pyrazolone-amides, phenylpyrazolones, and isoxazolone derivatives, obtained from sulphanilacetamidoazoacetoacetate(II) and sulphonophenylazoacetoacetate (III) by their reaction with hydrazine hydrate, semicarbazide acetate, phenylhydrazine, *p*-tolylhydrazine, *p*-chlorophenylhydrazine, and hydroxylamine acetate, are reported in Table I and Table II respectively.

TABLE I

Substituted pyrazolones, pyrazolone amide and isoxazolone from sulphanylacetamido-azoacetoacetate.

S. No.	3-Methyl-1... -4-sulphanilacet- amidoazo-5-pyra- zalone.	M.P.	Colour.	%Yield.	% Sulphur.	
					Found.	Reqd.
1	-5-pyrazolone	259°	Lemon-yellow	68	9.81	9.90
2	-1-amide-	230°	Pale yellow	69	8.87	8.74
3	-1-phenyl-	280°	Orange-red	72	7.91	8.02
4	-1-tolyl-	251°	Orange	70	7.68	7.74
5	-1- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-	240°	Orange-yellow	70	7.30	7.38
6	-5-isoxazolone	226°	Light yellow	65	9.79	9.87

TABLE II

Substituted pyrazolones, pyrazolone amide and isoxazolone from sulphonophenylazoacetoacetate.

S.No.	3-Methyl-1..... -4-sulphono- phenylazo-5- pyrazolone.	M.P.	Colour.	% Yield.	% Sulphur.	
					Found.	Reqd.
1	-5-pyrazolone	310°	Light yellow	69	11.21	11.34
2	-1-amide-	265°	Pale yellow	68	9.76	9.84
3	-1-phenyl-	290°	Orange-red	73	8.85	8.93
4	-1-tolyl-	273°	Orange-yellow	72	8.53	8.60
5	-1- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-	272°	Orange-red	72	8.09	8.15
6	-5-isoxazolone	260°	Lemon-yellow	70	11.19	11.30

Thanks of the authors are due to Dr. N. Anand for IR spectra.

SCHOOL OF CHEMISTRY,
MEERUT COLLEGE,
MEERUT.

Received November 9, 1963.